

Bilateral Trade between India and Afghanistan

Paper Id : 18427 Submission Date : 01/01/2024 Acceptance Date : 06/01/2024 Publication Date : 15/01/2024
This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10495394

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/resonance.php#8>

Gagandeep Kaur

Assistant Professor
Department Of Economics
Guru Nanak College
Sri Muktsar Sahib, Punjab,
India

Abstract

India and Afghanistan are the developing countries of the SAARC region. Foreign trade is a way to improve the bilateral relationship between two countries. This connection goes beyond governmental interactions, finding its roots in the historical exchanges between the people of both nations. The Strategic Partnership Agreement, signed in October 2011, further solidifies this relationship by outlining key areas of collaboration. This study has attempted to estimate India's bilateral trade relations with Afghanistan in terms of volume, composition and direction of trade. This study is based on secondary data for the period 2001-22. The study has been found that at present, India's trade with Afghanistan is US\$ 0.89 bn, of which India's export to Afghanistan are US\$ 0.48 bn and India's import from Afghanistan are US\$ 0.41 bn in 2022. It has been also found that India has huge trade potential with Afghanistan. The study predicts India's exports, imports and trade for the period 2001-22. It shows the increasing trend of India's trade with Afghanistan during the study period.

Keywords Afghanistan, Composition of Trade, Direction of Trade, India, Trade Volume.

Introduction

International trade plays a crucial role in fostering economic growth by expanding domestic economies to the global level. It contributes to economic prosperity through the reallocation of resources and comparative advantages, thereby facilitating overall economic development (Abendin & Duan, 2021). India and Afghanistan have a strong relationship based on historical and cultural affinities. This connection goes beyond governmental interactions, finding its roots in the historical exchanges between the people of both nations. The Strategic Partnership Agreement (SPA), signed in October 2011, further solidifies this relationship by outlining key areas of collaboration. Under the SPA, there is a commitment to assisting in the reconstruction of Afghanistan's infrastructure and institutions. India also extends support in the form of education and technical assistance to enhance indigenous Afghan capabilities across various sectors. Additionally, efforts are made to encourage investments in Afghanistan's natural resources. To promote economic ties, India grants duty-free access to the Indian market for exports from Afghanistan. The agreement emphasizes a commitment to an Afghan-led, Afghan-owned, broad-based, and inclusive process of peace and reconciliation. India advocates for sustained and long-term international commitment to Afghanistan. Regular high-level exchanges characterize the diplomatic ties between the two nations, underscoring the importance both countries place on maintaining a strong and enduring relationship (Ministry of External Affairs, 2017).

Aim of study

1. Analysis of trends of volume of trade between India and Afghanistan.
2. To analyze the balance of trade, composition of trade and direction of trade.
3. To suggest policy measures that would strengthen Indo-Afghanistan trade relations.

Review of Literature

In essence, the India-Afghanistan relationship is comprehensive, spanning economic, political, and cultural dimensions. The strategic partnership and collaborative initiatives reflect a shared commitment to mutual development and regional stability, positioning the two nations as strategic allies in the pursuit of common goals (Kiran and Madaan, 2022).

Methodology

The study is based on secondary data. Both published and unpublished sources of data are used. The data is mainly collected through various online and offline sources viz., Uncomtrade, World Bank, UN Publications, Economic survey of India and through various Books, Periodicals and Journals. Data related to composition of trade are based on Harmonized System (HS) coding at 6-digit level. The present paper attempted to analyze bilateral trade between India and Afghanistan for the period 2001-2022.

**Analysis Trade At Bilateral Level
Volume of Trade**

Afghanistan's bilateral trade with India has been growing steadily and got a big boost in recent years. Table 1 depicts the volume of bilateral trade between India and Afghanistan during 2001-22 at current prices. India's trade with Afghanistan increased from US\$ 40.8 mn in 2001 to US\$ 896.4 mn in 2022. Her total bilateral trade with Afghanistan accounted for US\$ 14086.0 mn during 2001-22. India's exports to Afghanistan have been growing faster than her imports from latter. India's exports to Afghanistan have increased from US\$ 20.9 mn in 2001 to US\$ 481.6 mn in 2022. As regards to India's imports from Afghanistan, these have increased from US\$ 19.9 mn during 2001 to US\$ 414.8 mn during 2022. As regards to India's trade balance with Afghanistan, table 1 shows that India's trade balance with latter was favourable throughout the study period. The highest trade surplus that India had with Afghanistan was US\$ 396.4 mn during 2019.

Table 1: India's Trade with Afghanistan during 2001-22

(US\$ million)

Year	India's Exports to Afghanistan	India's Imports from Afghanistan	Balance of Trade	Total Trade Turnover
2001	20.9	19.9	1.0	40.8
2002	50.1	17.4	32.7	67.5
2003	115.1	26.9	88.2	142.0
2004	167.7	53.2	114.5	220.9
2005	147.9	54.4	93.5	202.3
2006	170.6	46.6	124.0	217.2
2007	218.5	76.1	142.4	294.6
2008	364.9	133.1	231.8	498.0
2009	471.6	120.5	351.1	592.1
2010	392.6	143.7	248.9	536.3
2011	504.6	120.1	384.5	624.7
2012	475.6	79.7	395.9	555.3
2013	513.5	213.2	300.3	726.7
2014	442.9	243.7	199.2	686.6
2015	534.3	317.7	216.6	852.0
2016	473.0	282.3	190.7	755.3
2017	637.9	413.4	224.5	1051.3
2018	726.4	424.5	301.9	1150.9
2019	891.2	494.8	396.4	1386.0
2020	855.2	511.4	343.8	1366.6
2021	661.7	560.8	100.9	1222.5
2022	481.6	414.8	66.8	896.4
Total (2001-22)	9317.8	4768.2	4549.6	14086.0

Source: UN Comtrade Database (2023). <https://comtradeplus.un.org/TradeFlow>

Composition of Trade

An examination of inter-temporal changes in trade composition in the development process may provide useful insights into the evolving trade pattern of India and Afghanistan. With this purpose in view, traded commodities of these countries have classified adopting 6-digit HS classification. Table 2 presented the composition of India's exports to Afghanistan during 2001-22. Cane or beet sugar and chemically pure sucrose; Medicaments consisting of mixed or unmixed products; Vaccines for human medicine; Cumin seeds; Women's or girls' tracksuits and other garments; Woven fabrics; Nuts and other seeds; Wheat and meslin; Chewing tobacco, snuff and other manufactured tobacco, etc. are the major items of India's exports to Afghanistan during 2001-22. The exports of these major 30 commodities from India to Afghanistan were accounted for US\$ 8.3 mn in 2001 which increased to US\$ 194.7 mn in 2013 and US\$ 371.0 mn in 2022. However, India's total exports to Afghanistan were recorded at US\$ 20.9 in 2001 which increased to US\$ 513.5 mn in 2013 before declining to US\$ 481.6 mn in 2022.

